

An Energy-Efficient 56-Gb/s D-band TX-to-RX Link using CMOS ICs and Transmitarray Antennas

J. L. Gonzalez-Jimenez, *Senior Member, IEEE*, A. Siligaris, *Member, IEEE*, A. Hamani, F. Foglia Manzillo, *Member, IEEE*, P. Courouve, N. Cassiau, C. Dehos, A. Clemente, *Senior Member, IEEE*

1 Abstract— This paper presents an energy-efficient system with a transmitter and a receiver comprising multi-channel integrated circuits in 45-nm CMOS technology, in-package antenna feeds and high-directivity planar lenses. Data-rates up to 56 Gb/s are demonstrated over a 1-m point-to-point link using a full-digital communication system. The active circuits integrate multi-LO generators for implementing a channel-aggregation architecture that provides a large RF bandwidth using a significantly narrower baseband interface bandwidth. The energy consumption of the overall RF system is only 33 pJ/bit.

Index Terms— D-band, wireless link, channel aggregation, 16-QAM, CMOS 45nm, transmitarray, antenna-in-package.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH-data rate (approaching 100 Gb/s) wireless radio-frequency (RF) communication systems have been the subject of intensive research in the past years, driven by the increasing demand of high-capacity links for future networks (5G+, 6G). The D-band (110-170 GHz) has emerged as a convenient frequency range for these types of systems since it offers a good trade-off between available bandwidth (BW) and feasibility of advanced architectures using widespread silicon technologies.

Two main challenges arise in designing these systems: the possibility of covering very large bandwidths and the compensation of the high path loss, with the aim of achieving an acceptable overall energy consumption. The traditional solution based on phased arrays to increase the system gain has shown several limitations at D-band and beyond. Indeed, the active circuits hardly fit on the antenna array pitch [1]. Furthermore, some building blocks, such as the phase shifters, usually present narrowband operation, preventing a full exploitation of the available BW at those frequencies [2]-[4]. On the other hand, most reported broadband designs resort to a direct frequency down-conversion of wideband signals (tens of GHz) to baseband (BB). These architectures impose challenging constraints to the BB processor and data converter interfaces in terms of sampling frequency and power consumption.

I. SYSTEM LEVEL TRANSCIEVER ARCHITECTURE

A. Channel-aggregation TX and RX

¹This article was presented at the IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS 2024), Washington, DC, USA, June 16–21, 2024. This work was supported in part by COREnext project under EC grant agreement 101092598

The authors are with Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CEA, Leti, F-38000 Grenoble, France (e-mail: joseluis.gonzalezjimenez@cea.fr).

Achieving acceptable RF performance and power consumption becomes very challenging when the RF fractional BW to cover exceeds 20%. In this work, a channel-aggregation architecture is proposed for both the transmitter (TX) and the receiver (RX). Instead of keeping the same over-the-air signal BW at RF and BB, the transmitted full-band signal is the aggregation of narrower channels. The channel aggregation is performed in two steps: the first, from BB to intermediate frequency (IF), and the second from IF to the RF D-band, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The TX used in this work is built on the design presented in [6]. The RX is similar to the one in [7] and is detailed in Section II-A. The main drawback of a channel-aggregation architecture is that it often requires a large number of local oscillator (LO) signals to up- and down-convert all the channels from BB to RF, and *vice versa*. This work proposes a solution based on on-chip multi-LO generation technique [8]. The on-chip LOs are obtained by integer frequency multiplication from a common lower frequency reference, as indicated in Fig. 1. The reference is generated using commercial phased-locked loops (PLLs) without synchronization between the TX and RX. Note that all the LO signals of the two up-conversion stages of the TX are derived from the same PLL signal at 4.32 GHz.

B. Beamforming strategy

Phased-array architectures, enabling the control of the excitation of each radiating element (see Fig. 2a) are the often the solution of choice to form highly directive radiation

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the BB to D-band TX and D-band to IF RX.

Fig. 2. Beamforming alternatives: (a) phased array and (b) transmitarray.

> REPLACE THIS LINE WITH YOUR MANUSCRIPT ID NUMBER (DOUBLE-CLICK HERE TO EDIT) <

patterns. However, at frequencies beyond 100 GHz, it is hard to place circuits on a standard array lattice with half-a-wavelength pitches. Usually, for the active circuit driving each antenna only the RF front-end composed of the power amplifier (PA), low noise amplifier (LNA) and phase shifter (PS) fits, and this implies the use of extremely lossy signal distribution at the input of the array. It can be shown that at D-band the benefits of combining the output power of multiple PAs is hindered by the losses due to by the input signal distribution network for arrays comprising more than 64 elements spaced at half a wavelength, considering typical trace attenuation between 1 to 2 dB/cm. Another approach, followed in this work (see Fig. 2.b), consists in realizing the beamforming with a transmitarray antenna (TA) as described in [9]. The drawback of this technique is that there is a single focal-plane transmitter that has to provide the total power. However, larger TA radiating surfaces and longer focal distances can compensate a lower TX output power with an increased antenna gain.

II. TRANSCIVER DESCRIPTION AND PERFORMANCE

A. Receiver module

The RX module developed for the demonstration of the point-to-point link is shown in Fig. 3a. The RX circuit implementing the two-channel architecture shown in Fig. 1 is fabricated in a 45-nm CMOS technology and mounted on a low-cost printed circuit board (PCB), where the feed antennas, i.e. two pairs of aperture-coupled patches, are realized. The RX covers simultaneously two sub-bands: the lower band (LB), from 139 to 148 GHz, and the upper band (UB), from 148 to 157 GHz. The antenna-in-package (AiP) module is placed at the focal plane of a 40×40-element TA as shown in Fig. 3b. Each of the two feed antennas in the module is connected to one of the RX inputs. The measured gain at boresight of the AiP and of the entire antenna system are shown in Fig. 3c. The RX module (without the TA) is also characterized. The measured gain and

Fig. 3. (a) Receiver module and details of the antenna-in-package. (b) Transmitarray mounted over the antenna-in-package module. (c) Measured and simulated boresight antenna gain.

Fig. 4. (a) Measured and simulated receiver module gain and (b) noise figure.

noise figure (NF) are plotted in Fig. 4. Please, note that the measurements were performed over the air, so that the NF includes the AiP antenna gain (7 dBi). Fig. 3 and 4 report also simulations. The RX module simulated gain and NF include 3 dB of loss, accounting for the chip-to-board interconnection and the insertion loss of the antenna feed lines.

B. Transmitter module and link budget

The TX in the proposed point-to-point wireless builds on the work in [6]. It comprises the same AiP and TA of the RX. The IC output power at the antenna input ports is 0 dBm. The equivalent isotropic radiated power (EIRP) is 27 dBm at the output 1-dB compression point (OCP1dB) of the TX IC. Due to the multi-channel signal, a back-off of 9.4 dB is used, so that the effective EIRP for a modulated signal covering the full system band, i.e. from 139 to 157 GHz, is 15.4 dBm. The emitted signal is composed of eight BB channels, spaced by 2.16 GHz, which are up-converted to the D-band, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The TX circuit has two channels, as the RX, providing two sub-bands (LB and UB) to the two ports of the AiP. The full-band signal is obtained by the over-the-air power recombination of the two sub-band signals, performed by the TA. The phase profile of the TA is properly optimized to this purpose [9], considering the far fields emitted by the AiP.

C. Link budget

The link budget of Table 1 is obtained by combining the signal levels of the TX module and the NF and gain of the RX module. The table presents the signal and noise levels per channel and for the full band, when applicable. The calculations show that a 1-m link for 16-QAM modulated signal on all channels can be achieved. The target demodulated raw bit-error-rate (BER) is 10^{-2} , which requires an error vector magnitude (EVM) for 16-QAM of -15 dB (18%). The expected signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the RX is 26 dB, providing 9 dB of margin for RF impairments such as phase noise (jitter), I/Q imbalance, carrier

TABLE I. LINK BUDGET

Parameter	Per channel	Full band
BW (GHz)	2.16	IF: 2×4×2.16 RF 8×2.16
BB I or Q diff. peak amp. (mV @ 100 Ω)	650	
BB I or Q rms amp. (mV @ 100 Ω)	234	
BB to IF up-converter gain (dB)	-29	
IF connections losses (dB)	1	
IF signal power (dBm)	-30.5	-24.5 (×2)
D-band TX + antenna gain (dB)	37	
EIRP @ 1dBCP (dBm)	17	26
Back-off (dB)	9.4	
EIRP for IF power (dBm)	6.4	15.4
Path Loss @ 1 m (dB)	76	
Rx antenna gain (dBi)	26	
Rx NF at the antenna (dB)	12.5	
Rx signal @ antenna aperture (dBm)	-43.5	-34.5
Rx eq. noise @ antenna aperture (dBm)	-67.5	-58.5
SNR	24	
EVM for BER 10^{-2} on 16-QAM (dB)	-15	
Margin for other RF impairments (dB)	9	

> REPLACE THIS LINE WITH YOUR MANUSCRIPT ID NUMBER (DOUBLE-CLICK HERE TO EDIT) <

frequency offset (CFO) and channel-to-channel interference. Among these factors, jitter and channel-to-channel interference have been shown to be the most limiting ones [10].

The phase noise (PhN) induced jitter is investigated in Fig. 5, that shows the PhN measured at the RX for carriers at the center of the lowest and highest channels of each sub-band. This PhN is cumulated from the LOs of the TX and the RX. The measured double sideband (DSB) integrated rms jitter is 1.8 fs. This jitter value alone would prevent receiving correctly a 16-QAM signal since the EVM for a SNR=26 dB is -3 dB. In order to reduce this jitter, the waveform sent by the TX contains pilots scattered across the modulated payload. They are used in the RX at digital BB (DBB) to track and compensate slow phase wandering. This technique is effective up to a certain offset frequency from the carrier, and acts effectively as a high-pass filter for the phase noise, resulting in a mitigation of the time jitter, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The scattered pilots time offset used in the TX DBB corresponds to a filter cut-off of 10 MHz, providing a final jitter of 400 fs, which enables correct demodulation for 16-QAM. Please, note that these results correspond to extremely low-PhN multi-LO signals. The measured cumulated phase noise of the overall wireless system (TX and RX) is -95 dBc/Hz at 1 MHz offset. The noise floor is about -110 dBc/Hz and is generated from commercial PLLs, not from laboratory bench top equipment.

III. POINT-TO-POINT LINK SYSTEM-LEVEL DEMONSTRATION

The TX and RX modules described in Section II are combined in a system-level implementation of a point-to-point link, as illustrated in Fig. 6 for a 1-m range. The TX and RX DBB sections are implemented in MATLAB. The multiple BB inputs of the TX come from a multi-channel arbitrary waveform generator (not shown in Fig. 6). The IF signals at the two outputs of the RX are sampled using a 200 MS/s digital sampling scope (DSO) and sent to the DBB RX. A 20 dB-gain V-band LNA is used between the RX and the scope in order to compensate the attenuation due to the module output traces and cables. The computer screen in Fig. 6 shows the demodulated constellations for the 4 channels of one of the two sub-bands. The other sub-band is received simultaneously on the spectrum analyzer. The received signal spectrum for the two sub-band outputs of the RX and the corresponding constellations are shown in Fig. 7. The overall data-rate is 56 Gb/s: 7 Gb/s for each of the 8 BB channels carrying 1.75 Gbauds of 16-QAM modulated signals. The average EVM is lower than -15 dB and

Fig. 5. TX+RX phase noise and jitter measured on the received carriers.

the overall BER for the four combined signals of both LB and UB outputs is 10^{-2} .

A further investigation of EVM limiting components is presented in Fig. 8. First, the distance link is varied from 20 cm up to 1.5 m and the BER is measured for the two bands at the output of the RX. These results are compared to the BER computed using the theoretical 16-QAM bit-error probability, considering that the EVM is set only by the SNR calculated

Fig. 6. Point-to-point 1-m link demonstration setup.

Fig. 7. (a) Received signals at both LB and UB IF outputs against their corresponding D-band frequencies. Demodulated 16-QAM constellations for (b) the four LB channels, and (c) the four UB channels.

Fig. 8. Comparison of measured BER and values calculated from the EVM.

> REPLACE THIS LINE WITH YOUR MANUSCRIPT ID NUMBER (DOUBLE-CLICK HERE TO EDIT) <

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF THIS WORK WITH OTHER RECENTLY REPORTED D-BAND WIRELESS LINKS.

	This work	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Module Technology	BB TX/RX + TA beamformer	RF phased array antenna on board	RF phased array antenna on board	RF phased array antenna on board	RF phased array antenna on chip + lens
IC Technology	45-nm RFSOI	45-nm RFSOI	45-nm RFSOI	55-nm BiCMOS	130-nm SiGe
Frequency (GHz)	139-157	144	135-142.5	140-160	110-170
EIRP OCP1dB (dBm)	27	17	32.5	26***	NA
RF Tx/Rx Gain (dB)	10/25	n.a.	44/20	15/8	8.4/22
RX NF (dB)	5*	10	6.2	15.6	10.08
Tx+Rx P _{DC} (mW)	1580+400	3816**	13000+6700**	3400+4900**	2500+1950**
Energy eff.	33 pJ/b	1192 pJ/b**	985 pJ/b**	159 nJ/b**	22.25 pJ/b**
N. signal CHs × BW (GHz)	8 × 2.16	1 × 2	1 × 2	1 × 0.0625	1 × 40
Modulation DR(Gb/s)@ EVM at distance	16-QAM 56@18% at 1 m	QPSK 3.15@20% at 1m	16-QAM 20@9% at 1.45m 16-QAM 16@16% at 5.2m	QPSK 0.052@NA at 34 cm	32-QAM 200@8.3% at 15 cm
Link Type	TX/RX with 27 dBi 40×40 TA beamformer	RF 4-ant TX and 4-ant RX 17dBi beamformers	RF 8-ant TX and 8-ant RX beamformers.	RF 16-ant TX and 16-ant RX beamformers	RF 4-ant TX and RX beamformers+lenses

* Includes antenna-in-package gain of ~7 dBi. ** LO generation not included. *** Peak EIRP

from the link budget at the various distances (e.g. 26 dB at 1 m) and the filtered rms jitter obtained from the phase noise measurements (400 fs). The results match the calculations if 6 dB are removed from the SNR. This value is consistent with the SNR observed in the spectra of Fig. 7a and is attributed mainly to channel-to-channel interferences due to the LO spurs at adjacent channels and to the other RF imperfections. Indeed, the TX signal waveform includes some preambles that allow to estimate some of these imperfections in the RX DBB. The CFO measured in the different channels varies from 200 kHz to 300 kHz, depending on the channel. The I/Q imbalance is smaller than 0.5 dB in amplitude and 5° in phase, for all channels.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates a D-band wireless link from digital BB to digital BB achieving 56 Gb/s data-rate. The innovative TX and RX are based on a channel-aggregation architecture that relaxes the BW constraints of the RF circuitry and reduces the digital BB interfaces sampling frequency. An energy efficiency of 33 pJ/b for the overall RF system (TX + RX) is achieved. The TX and RX use in-package antennas and flat discrete lenses (transmitarrays) in PCB for wideband beamforming. The implemented TA has a fixed phase distribution but promising alternative designs including switches could enable extremely low-power electronic beamsteering [11].

The TX radiates an EIRP of 27 dBm at the 1-dB OCP1dB. A BER before channel decoding of 10⁻², based on an EVM equal or better than -15 dB (18%), is achieved at a 1-m distance with non-synchronized TX and RX by using on-chip multi-LO generation from external commercial PLLs. The proposed TX and RX convey a larger data-rate and operate over a wider band than recently reported D-band link transceivers [2]-[4], as shown in Table 2. Compared to [5], that demonstrates a higher data-rate but requires digital interfaces with sampling frequencies in the range of 80 GS/s at least, the proposed system provides a much lower BB interface BW (only 2.16 GHz), paving the way to energy efficient, extremely high-throughput wireless links.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Sadhu, X. Gu and A. Valdes-Garcia, "The more (antennas), the merrier: a Survey of silicon-based mm-wave phased arrays using multi-IC scaling," *IEEE Microw. Mag.*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 32-50, Dec. 2019.
- [2] S. Abu-Surra *et al.*, "End-to-end 140 GHz wireless link demonstration with fully-Digital beamformed system," *2021 IEEE Int. Conf. Commun. Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, 2021, pp. 1-6.
- [3] A. Ahmed, L. Li, M. Jung, G. M. Rebeiz, "A 140 GHz scalable on-grid 8×8-element transmit-receive phased-array with up/down converters and 64QAM/24 Gbps data rates," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp. (RFIC)*, Jun. 2023, pp. 97–100, pp. 93-96.
- [4] D. del Rio *et al.*, "A D-Band 16-element phased-array transceiver in 55-nm BiCMOS," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 854-869, Feb. 2023.
- [5] A. Karakuzulu, W. A. Ahmad, D. Kissinger, A. Malignaggi, "A four-channel bidirectional D-Band phased-array transceiver for 200 Gb/s 6G wireless communications in a 130-nm BiCMOS technology," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circ.*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 1310-1322, May 2023.
- [6] J. L. Gonzalez-Jimenez *et al.*, "A 57.6 Gb/s wireless link based on a 26.4 dBm EIRP D-band transmitter module and a channel aggregation chipset on CMOS 45 nm," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp. (RFIC)*, Jun. 2023, pp. 97–100.
- [7] A. Hamani, *et al.*, "A 56.32 Gb/s 16-QAM D-band wireless link using RX-TX systems-in-package with Integrated multi-LO generators in 45nm RFSOI," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp. (RFIC)*, Jun. 2022, pp. 75-78.
- [8] A. Siligaris *et al.*, "A Multichannel programmable high order frequency multiplier for channel bonding and full duplex transceivers at 60 GHz band," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circ. Symp. (RFIC)*, Aug. 2020, pp. 259-262.
- [9] F. Foglia Manzillo *et al.*, "A 28 dBm-EIRP low-profile D-band transmitting module with a folded transmitarray antenna," *IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Symp. Dig.*, Jun. 2023, pp. 311-314.
- [10] J. L. Gonzalez-Jimenez *et al.*, "Channel-aggregation CMOS transceiver for 100 Gbps wireless point-to-point links," *J. Wireless Commun. Netw.*, vol. 117, pp. 1–21, Jun. 2020.
- [11] S. Venkatesh, X. Lu, H. Saecidi, and K. Sengupta, "A high-speed programmable and scalable terahertz holographic metasurface based on tiled CMOS chips," *Nature Electron.*, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 785–793, Dec. 2020.